

INFLUENCE OF SEED AND MINERAL FERTILIZER RATES ON PLANT DENSITIES OF CROTALARIA

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Abstract: This article discusses the effects of sowing rates and mineral fertilizer application rates on the seedling density of the unconventional leguminous crop, *Crotalaria*, grown under the typical gray soil conditions of the Tashkent region. It has been scientifically substantiated that increasing the sowing rate from 10 kg/ha to 18 kg/ha reduces plant mortality by 0.5-1.2%. Similarly, when the mineral fertilizer rates are increased from N60 P90 K60 kg/ha to N90 P135 K90 kg/ha, seedling survival improves by 0.1% to 0.3%. Further increasing the rates to N120 P180 K120 kg/ha enhances seedling survival by 0.3% to 0.6%.

Introduction

In recent years, global agricultural practices have focused on selecting crop types that are compatible with soil and climatic conditions by considering their biological characteristics. This has led to the continuous improvement of crop structures and the development of agrotechnologies to enhance soil fertility. Additionally, effective use of modern technologies has enabled the preservation and improvement of soil fertility properties, ensuring abundant and high-quality crop yields. By optimizing mineral fertilizer usage, particularly in cotton cultivation, it has become possible to reduce production costs and increase efficiency.

In our country, the current situation demands expanding the food base, fully utilizing soil-protecting and fertility-enhancing measures in a timely and comprehensive manner, and paying greater attention to the proper selection and placement of crop varieties in agriculture.

Crotalaria is considered an unconventional crop in our country, but it is primarily used as a fiber crop in foreign countries. Several international researchers, including Cook et al. and Hargrove [3, 4], have conducted studies on its use as a natural fiber and green manure. For fiber production, *Crotalaria* is harvested during its full flowering stage, which occurs 75-80 days after sowing. The fiber yield is obtained from two harvests, producing 4-6 tons of dry stalks per hectare, from which 300-600 kg/ha of fiber can be extracted.

The *Crotalaria juncea* plant is biologically adapted to diverse soil and climatic conditions. Its seeds can be used as food products, while its hay serves as high-calorie feed for livestock. In agriculture, it is used to enhance soil fertility and improve soil reclamation conditions. Additionally, it has applications in medicine for treating various diseases, in apiculture as a nectar source, and in the light industry as a source of fiber [5, 6].

According to G. Yoqubov et al. [7], in the soil and climatic conditions of the Khorezm region, sowing 18 kg of seeds per hectare in the last ten days of April is considered an optimal time and rate for producing green mass. During the growing season, it is possible to obtain up to 60 tons/ha of green mass yield.

Crotalaria plays an important role in crop rotation systems due to its ability to eliminate nematodes, accumulate nitrogen in a short period, and generate significant biomass [2]. When sown after cereal crops, it covers the soil surface, reducing moisture loss while simultaneously accumulating large amounts of nitrogen and biomass [1].

Considering that *Crotalaria* not only fulfills the diverse needs of our population but also remains insufficiently studied from a scientific perspective, it is crucial to develop and refine its cultivation technologies. Moreover, the implementation of these results into agricultural practices is considered a pressing issue.

Research Results. Field experiments were conducted on typical gray soils of Tashkent region during 2022–2024 to study the effects of seed sowing rates and mineral fertilizer application rates on the planting density of *crotalaria*

According to the data obtained in 2023, the planting density of *crotalaria* at the beginning of the growing period was as follows: in the options sown at 10 kg/ha, it ranged from 218,750 to 220,000 plants; in the options sown at 14 kg/ha, it ranged from 311,050 to 315,700 plants; and in the options sown at 18 kg/ha, it ranged from 416,250 to 418,950 plants. By the end of the growing period, these figures had decreased, with the options sown at 10 kg/ha showing a density of 204,093 to 207,460 plants, those sown at 14 kg/ha showing 289,587 to 296,442 plants, and those sown at 18 kg/ha showing 385,447 to 390,042 plants. It was determined that both seed sowing rates and mineral fertilizer application rates had a direct impact on the planting density of *crotalaria*. In the experiments, the mortality rate of plants by the end of the growing period for options with a sowing rate of 10 kg/ha was 6.7%, 6.3%, 6.0%, and 5.7%, respectively. For the options sown at 14 kg/ha (options 5, 6, 7, and 8), the mortality rates were 6.9%, 6.7%, 6.6%, and 6.1%, respectively. For the options sown at 18 kg/ha (options 9, 10, 11, and 12), the mortality rates were 7.4%,

7.2%, 7.1%, and 6.9%, respectively. Analysis of the data revealed that increasing the sowing rate of crotalaria by 4 kg/ha (to 14 kg/ha) compared to 10 kg/ha led to an increase in plant mortality by

Table 1

Planting Density of Crotalaria (2022–2024)

Options	Theoretical planting density, thousand bush/ha	Rate of mineral fertilizers, kg/ha	Seedling density, thousand /ha		Seedling preservation, %	Seedling death, %
			beginning of the period	end of the period		
2022 year.						
1-option	250 (10 kg/ha)	Without fertilizer	225075	210500	93.5	6.5
2- option		N ₆₀ P ₉₀ K ₆₀	231025	217394	94.1	5.9
3- option		N ₉₀ P ₁₃₅ K ₉₀	232005	218780	94.3	5.7
4- option		N ₁₂₀ P ₁₈₀ K ₁₂₀	236005	223496	94.7	5.3
5- option	350 (14 kg/ha)	Without fertilizer	329000	303996	92.4	7.6
6- option		N ₆₀ P ₉₀ K ₆₀	331095	309371	93.5	6.5
7- option		N ₉₀ P ₁₃₅ K ₉₀	340095	319039	93.9	6.1
8- option		N ₁₂₀ P ₁₈₀ K ₁₂₀	342000	322192	94.3	5.7
9- option	450 (18 kg/ha)	Without fertilizer	434025	400432	92.2	7.8
10- option		N ₆₀ P ₉₀ K ₆₀	441002	411091	93.3	6.7
11- option		N ₉₀ P ₁₃₅ K ₉₀	443045	414655	93.5	6.5
12- option		N ₁₂₀ P ₁₈₀ K ₁₂₀	447006	418576	93.7	6.3
2023 year						
1-option	250 (10 kg/ha)	Without fertilizer	218750	204093	93.3	6.7
2- option		N ₆₀ P ₉₀ K ₆₀	219500	205671	93.7	6.3
3- option		N ₉₀ P ₁₃₅ K ₉₀	220000	206800	94.0	6.0
4- option		N ₁₂₀ P ₁₈₀ K ₁₂₀	220000	207460	94.3	5.7
5- option	350 (14 kg/ha)	Without fertilizer	311050	289587	93.1	6.9
6- option		N ₆₀ P ₉₀ K ₆₀	316400	298466	93.3	6.7
7- option		N ₉₀ P ₁₃₅ K ₉₀	317450	296498	93.4	6.6
8- option		N ₁₂₀ P ₁₈₀ K ₁₂₀	315700	296442	93.9	6.1
9- option	450 (18 kg/ha)	Without fertilizer	416250	385447	92.6	7.4
10- option		N ₆₀ P ₉₀ K ₆₀	417150	387115	92.8	7.2
11- option		N ₉₀ P ₁₃₅ K ₉₀	418500	388786	92.9	7.1
12- option		N ₁₂₀ P ₁₈₀ K ₁₂₀	418950	390042	93.1	6.9
2024 year						
1-option	250 (10 kg/ha)	ЎҒИТСИЗ	215250	197599	91.8	8.2
2- option		N ₆₀ P ₉₀ K ₆₀	217000	200725	92.5	7.5
3- option		N ₉₀ P ₁₃₅ K ₉₀	219000	204108	93.2	6.8
4- option		N ₁₂₀ P ₁₈₀ K ₁₂₀	219750	205246	93.4	6.6
5- option	350 (14 kg/ha)	Without fertilizer	313500	286672	91.5	8.5
6- option		N ₆₀ P ₉₀ K ₆₀	313600	289139	92.2	7.8
7- option		N ₉₀ P ₁₃₅ K ₉₀	316400	292986	92.6	7.4
8- option		N ₁₂₀ P ₁₈₀ K ₁₂₀	315700	293285	92.9	7.1
9- option	450 (18 kg/ha)	Without fertilizer	409950	374694	91.4	8.6
10- option		N ₆₀ P ₉₀ K ₆₀	411750	377163	91.6	8.4
11- option		N ₉₀ P ₁₃₅ K ₉₀	414000	380052	91.8	8.2
12- option		N ₁₂₀ P ₁₈₀ K ₁₂₀	414900	382123	92.1	7.9

0.2–0.6%. Similarly, increasing the sowing rate by 8 kg/ha (to 18 kg/ha) resulted in an increase in plant mortality by 0.5–1.2%.

Thus, when the sowing rate of crotalaria is increased by 4 kg/ha (to 14 kg/ha) compared to 10 kg/ha, plant mortality is recorded at 0.2–0.6%. When the rate is increased by 8 kg/ha (to 18 kg/ha), plant mortality rises to 0.5–1.2%.

In general, a decrease of approximately 15,000–25,000 plants per hectare was observed from the beginning to the end of the growing season. This reduction in plant density may be attributed to inter-row cultivation practices and the influence of other external factors.

These patterns were also observed in 2022 and 2024. However, in 2024, due to higher levels of rainfall, the plant mortality rate was 1–2% higher compared to 2022 and 2023.

Data on the impact of mineral fertilizers on the planting density of crotalaria showed that increasing the application rates of mineral fertilizers in plant care led to an improvement in plant retention rates.

According to the data obtained, the mortality rate of crotalaria plants was higher in the options where no fertilizers were applied, with rates recorded at 6.7%, 6.9%, and 7.4%, respectively.

Thus, as with other crops, the absence of fertilizer application in the cultivation of crotalaria negatively affects the retention of plant density.

When mineral fertilizers were applied at a rate of N60 P90 K60 kg/ha, plant mortality by the end of the growing period was recorded at 6.3%, 6.7%, and 7.2% for options 2, 6, and 10, respectively. For the options where fertilizers were applied at a rate of N90 P135 K90 kg/ha (options 3, 7, and 11), the mortality rates were 6.0%, 6.6%, and 7.1%, respectively. When a higher rate of fertilizers, N120 P180 K120 kg/ha, was applied (options 4, 8, and 12), the mortality rates decreased further to 5.7%, 6.1%, and 6.9%.

The data clearly shows that increasing fertilizer rates from N60 P90 K60 kg/ha to N90 P135 K90 kg/ha reduced plant mortality by 0.1% to 0.3%. Further increasing the rate to N120 P180 K120 kg/ha improved plant retention by an additional 0.3% to 0.6%.

The same patterns were observed in the data obtained in 2022 and 2024 (see table).

Conclusion. In the conditions of typical gray soils of the Tashkent region, increasing the sowing rate of crotalaria from 10 kg/ha to 14 kg/ha results in plant mortality of 0.2–0.6%. When the sowing rate is increased to 18 kg/ha, mortality reaches 0.5–1.2%.

In plant care, increasing the mineral fertilizer application rate from N60 P90 K60 kg/ha to N90 P135 K90 kg/ha reduces plant mortality by 0.1–0.3%. Further

increasing the fertilizer rate to N120 P180 K120 kg/ha ensures a reduction in plant mortality by 0.3–0.6%.

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